

SWAYAM ONLINE COURSE CERTIFICATE CUM MARKSHEET

This Certificate is awarded to

DR. BULLA THIRUMALES

for successfully completing the 4 credit course

Goods and Services Tax

*(offered by Dr. Ashoka M. L, Assistant Professor, Department of Post Graduate Studies in
Commerce, University of Mysore, Mysore, Karnataka)*

in the proctored examination held on **09.11.2019** for the session July-October 2019.

Roll No.	Internal Assessment (out of 30)	Proctored Examination (out of 70)	Total Marks Obtained (out of 100)
	Marks Obtained	Marks Obtained	
203188	26	43	69

N. Gopukumar
Joint Secretary, UGC
National Coordinator

Prof. K.M. Mahadevan
Registrar (Evaluation)
University of Mysore, Mysore, Karnataka